

Cyclic Compounds. Part II. On the Constitution of the Ketonic Mannich Base Derived from Isobutyl Methyl Ketone

P. C. Bhattacharyya

The action of paraformaldehyde and diethylamine hydrochloride on isobutyl methyl ketone has been studied. Malonic ester on alkylation¹ with the methiodide of this ketonic Mannich base, followed by hydrolysis, esterification, and internal condensation^{2a,2b}, provides chiefly 1-isopropylcyclohexane-2,6-dione (III), thus indicating the formation of 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (I).

In connection with another investigation, a supply 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (I) in moderate quantity was required. A direct application of the ketonic Mannich base, derived from isobutyl methyl ketone, without a proof to the constitution of the product, seemed to be very undesirable. Isobutyl methyl ketone with paraformaldehyde and diethylamine hydrochloride may form either (I) or (V).

Diethyl malonate on alkylation with the methiodide of this ketonic Mannich base, followed by hydrolysis, esterification, and internal condensation², formed chiefly the cyclic dione (III) and not (VI)^{2b} as was to be expected when 1-diethylamino-3-methyl-2-acetylbutane (V) was the main product of reaction by the action of paraformaldehyde and diethylamine hydrochloride on isobutyl methyl ketone.

1. Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 848.

2a. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1288; 1936, 50, 192, 747, 1079.

2b. Bardhan *et al. ibid.*, 1951, 3195; 1963, 2402.

At the start, it was planned to begin with the hydrogenated product of 1-diethylamino-5-methylhex-4-en-3-one (II). Curiously, the foregoing compound on hydrogenation³ afforded 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (I) in poor yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

*1-Diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (I)*⁴.—A mixture of isobutyl methyl ketone (25 g.), diethylamine hydrochloride (35.58 g.), paraformaldehyde (9.9 g.), HCl (conc., 0.5 ml), and ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The ethanol was removed on the water bath; the residue was cooled and treated with water (10 ml) and a solution of KOH (30 g.) in water (15 ml). The resulting solution was shaken, saturated with anhydrous potassium carbonate, filtered, and washed with ether. The ether extract was once washed with water, dried (CaCl₂), and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation furnished colorless 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane (32 g.) b.p. 93-94°/6 mm (bath 135-40°). (Found: C, 71.30; H, 12.50. C₁₁H₂₃ON requires C, 71.35; H, 12.43%).

1-Diethylamino-5-methylhex-4-en-3-one (II).—A mixture of mesityl oxide (24.5 g.), diethylamine hydrochloride (35.58 g.), paraformaldehyde (9.9 g.), HCl (conc., 5 ml), and ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The ethanol was removed and the residue was treated with water (10 ml), followed by a solution of KOH (30 g.) in water (15 ml). The resulting mixture was saturated with anhydrous potassium carbonate, filtered, and washed with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (CaCl₂), and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation provided the colorless ketone (II) (30.5 g.), b.p. 105-108°/6 mm (bath 135-40°). (Found: C, 72.12; H, 11.49. C₁₁H₂₁ON requires C, 72.13; H, 11.47%).

This amino-ketone (20 g.) was hydrogenated in presence of palladous chloride (0.1 g.) and gum arabic (0.1 g.) in a little of water (5 ml) till the calculated quantity of hydrogen (2750 ml) was taken up. The catalyst was filtered, washed with ether, and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation furnished colorless 1-diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane(I) (9.2 g.), b.p. 92-95°/6 mm.

Ethyl 7-Methyl-5-oxo-2-ethoxycarboxyloctanoate (IV: R=CO₂Et).—Diethyl malonate (16 g.) was added to a solution, prepared from sodium (2.3 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (40 ml). 1-Diethylamino-5-methyl-3-oxohexane methiodide, prepared from amino-ketone (I) (18.5 g.) and methyl iodide (7.2 ml) in a little of anhydrous ethanol, was added to it. After 12 hr. at the room temperature, the mixture was gently refluxed for 6 hr. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, and acidified with HCl (conc., 15 ml). The oil was taken in ether, the ether extract was washed with water, dried (CaCl₂), and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation provided a viscous oil (17.5 g.), b.p. 145-50°/4mm. (Found: C, 61.72; H, 8.90. C₁₄H₂₄O₅ requires C, 61.76; H, 8.82%).

3. *Arch. Pharm.*, 1928, 265, 684.

4. Cf. "Organic Syntheses", Vol. 23, p. 30.

Ethyl 7-Methyl-5-oxo-octanoate (IV: R=H).—The preceding oxo-ester (17.5 g.), KOH (11 g.) in water (11 ml), and spirit (99 ml) were refluxed on a steam bath for 1 hr. The ethanol was removed on a water bath; the residue was cooled and extracted with ether. The alkaline solution was acidified with HCl (conc., 20 ml) and the separated oil was taken in ether. The solvent was removed and the crude acid (15.7 g.) was heated in an oil bath (125-130°) till the evolution of CO₂ had completely ceased. The residue (11.2 g.) on esterification with ethanolic HCl afforded the colorless ester (9 g.), b.p. 120-22°/5 mm. (Found: C, 65.97; H, 10.10. C₁₁H₂₀O₃ requires C, 66.00; H, 10.00%).

1-Isopropylcyclohexane-2,6-dione (III).—To sodium (0.93 g.), dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml), the preceding oxo-ester (IV: R=H) (7.3 g.) was added in the cold. The resulting mixture was heated on a steam bath for 30 hr. The residue was cooled, water was added, and shaken till a clear solution was obtained. Ethanol was removed and the residue was cooled and extracted with ether. The alkaline solution was acidified and the precipitated crystals were collected, washed, and dried. *1-Isopropylcyclohexane 2,6-dione* melted at 140-43°. (Found: C, 70.10; H, 9.10. C₉H₁₄O₂ requires C, 70.13; H, 9.09%). Bardhan *et al*^{1b} recorded m.p. 106-107° for compound (VI).

The author is indebted to late Dr. J. C. Bardhan for his advice and encouragement during the course of the investigation.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
VIDYASAGAR COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received January 21, 1965.